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Playing safe in teaching?

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INTRODUCTION

Fluidity and the rapid pace of development in science and technology as well as concern for the welfare of both humans and their environment leads to increasing requirements of adaptability in working life [1]; [2]. This calls for changes to higher education as well [3]. Teaching should not only be individual and one-substance centered; it must rather support collective learning, creativity, and solution-oriented approach in a multidiscipline environment without losing its roots in knowledge-based targets and scientific theories.

There are more sources of information constantly available than ever before and therefore, emphasis is trending towards students' free and active inventing and experimenting. Testing possibilities and limits in utilizing novel technologies and/or in utilizing complex combinations of competencies in student team settings offer memorable learning experiences. This will require creating a culture where aiming for good results, accepting contradicting ideas and taking failure as an opportunity to learn something new all co-exist and prosper.

Typically, the exercises, results and solutions used in university level education are well known beforehand, i.e. safe for teachers, but not ill-defined and/or open-ended problems like those that they tend to be in real life. However, the possibility to go to an unknown area in teaching and learning provides an effective learning context where failure, as well as success, is an option to learn and create something new. A balance of passive retention of information during education along with active, self-motivated investigation of an area by a student can result in a profound difference in both their retention of the experience and their development of an ability to innovate.

In this paper, we refer to innovations, inventions and creativity acknowledging their differences by definition and by research traditions. We rely on the alignment of these terms; inventions may lead to innovations and creativity is a helpful feature in both of this processes.

This paper invites university teachers to reflect and investigate their own teaching, and university teaching in general. How often there are so-called real-life exercises where starting point and problem parameters are not well defined, and a solution is not known beforehand by anyone, not even by teachers? In what extent university studies support students' creativity and inventions?

1 TEACHING

1.1 Working life requirements

In recent years, there has been a lot of discussion about working life skills in education. The core of engineering education lies on numerical skills, i.e. knowledge in science, technology, engineering and mathematics. In addition to that, working life skills such as problem solving, initiative, communication, collaboration, IT and media skills are needed [4]. Critical and analytical thinking, creativity and innovation skills, ethics, leadership and desire to lifelong learning, among many others are also often considered as requirements of working life today [5], [6].

During studies, the role of student is to learn the issues being taught. Students are sometimes considered as a kind of passive product of universities, in a strictly defined frame. Modern easy access to and a culture of reliance on online sourced information can lead toward a more passive acceptance of the flow of information without the need

for active participation of acquiring it, leaving the student without sufficient resources to cope with contingencies in life and the workplace. In working life, however, graduated students are expected to be not just well informed, but also innovative and creative.

There are more than 600000 engineering students in Europe [7]; would it be possible to support and exploit their innovation potential before the graduation instead of after? A university oriented as a supporting environment may provide good baseline for invention production, as there are presumably numerous different disciplines with sources into the knowledge of the latest technological developments available.

1.2 University courses

Worldwide development of education systems is in need of better ways to respond to the changing world. It is not enough just to learn standard requirements. In fact, it is even more important to equip the learners to take an active role, initiate investigations, be creative, seek new knowledge and manage risk as they face new challenges. Key and fundamental engineering competencies for the future are best developed through education given in university courses. Therefore, working life skills are often taught in separate courses, or integrated courses where theory and practice meet.

In basic courses, the instructor is very familiar with both the problem and the solution. In more advanced courses, the instructor knows at least the process of how to move towards the solution. However, the presumption here is that the solution exists and is reasonable. Quality systems related to teaching often mean, for example, well defined learning outcomes, and clear and safe standard processes in teaching; that is, the desired learning outcome is set beforehand and is known to be provable.

Situative perspective on learning has gained more interest during the recent years. The focus there is not on mental structures of individual learner as such but on learning in activity systems that comprise several people and a variety of technologies being available [8]. This view stresses the importance of the surrounding context in problem solving and there are notions that skilled problem solving incorporates the environment, i.e. people, things, and information, into the actual technical problem-solving system [9]. This view is present with courses where the surrounding world plays an important role in the courses, as a source of problems, as a catalyst or as a source of solutions and resources. The situational or contextual view means that problems and exercises are ill-defined and open-ended and they carry the complexity and dynamism of real life with them. The student's investigation into that fluid environment is forced into a more active, rather than passive behaviour, and as such is more likely to internalize the experience, especially given what happens when the student inevitably fails. This prompts further investigations, questions about the reason for the failure, which cements the experience in the student's mind and drives innovation.

In this paper, we go even further and posit that students might not just try to learn working life skill or methodologies supporting innovation in the university in order to use the skills later at work, but they actually could produce new ideas and inventions during their study time. The world would not happen later; it would already be present at the university.

2 INVENTING

2.1 Offering possibilities

One way to offer possibilities to produce inventions and innovations is to increase student participation to R&D actions in universities: a student's role is changed to be more active if he/she is a part of a creative team [10]. Learning processes will be turned from standardized individual substance teaching or memorization to a collective learning, creativity and solution orientation, without losing strong theory basis or learning goals. The learning outcomes that are defined beforehand will be connected to open, innovative and practice oriented testing. Thus, theory and practice will integrate strongly.

When multidisciplinary and multi-professional teams that include several different nationalities solve ill-defined and open-ended problems, moving ahead to the solution requires and simultaneously develops a variety of different skills. Besides substance know-how, other skills like communication, team working, problem solving and creativity are important in working life, as well as other sectors of life in general.

When facing a totally new type of problem, there are no right ways to proceed or right answers that are known beforehand. This means that students have all options present: failure is always a possibility as well as are remarkable success. Besides that, everything in between can be interpreted as partially successful results in the sense of learning the tools needed to succeed. In all different options mentioned above, students have a possibility to learn - sometimes even unexpected things, and opportunities to invent novel solutions. Of course, this kind of arrangement at a university course means that a course instructor has all the same options in his/her teaching work.

2.2 Combining social aspects and technologies in fostering creativity

Importance of exploration and possibility to fail are recognized in research on innovation and creativity, and the concepts of "failure value" and "fast failure" are used to highlight the elementary importance of learning. The first theoretical process models of innovation and/or creativity were linear, but those processes are nowadays considered nonlinear and interactive.

The famous system model of creativity [11] proposes that creativity is a dynamic, reflective interaction between an individual, a domain and society. In our setting, a domain could mean, for example, a specific branch or field of technology. The co-existence of two aspects, social and science based, has been present for decades in innovation research, and fostering innovation means that there are impulses coming from these two directions, social and science, i.e. technology.

In order to foster innovation, it is important to integrate different types of backgrounds, knowledge, competences, experiences and technologies together. If the participants represent different kinds of technological knowhow, there are more possibilities to learn and innovate, but it should be noticed that people like to work in groups made up of members that are similar in some way to themselves. Ability to work in differing and heterogeneous groups seems to be rather uncommon, and the role of a facilitator or broker is sometimes relevant. It may be counterintuitive that non-homogenous or a diverse group of members would be a productive model to encourage, but it is possible or even likely that diverse outlooks or points of view can support or help produce

innovations by causing the students to defend and clarify their positions or ideas to their team members. Individuals who have a different point of view may disagree with their team members and will question them, and while it can cause friction or discord, it can also be a powerful source of innovation. A group of people all of like mind won't have as much motivation to do that, and may follow more of a herd mentality, which is by definition not innovative. In any case, success in innovation depends on the flexibility of the organization and their ability to interact with environment [12].

Ability to follow and scan the environment is a central doctrine in business studies, e.g. marketing, and it is visible in successful innovation processes. A previous study [13] stated that achieving something new often requires going outside the established channels. This is challenging to a university system, which very much builds on the division of different fields of science in both research and education. Crossing those borders is not common or encouraged in the pigeon holed world of universities. It is also generally found that the more radical and risky ideas are, the more there will be organizational resistance [14].

Previous research on innovation, invention or creativity proves that organizations seldom push themselves into directions of accelerated creativity. We might assume that this could also be the case in university courses. Pushing inventing or creativity further may be more likely to be limited and only competence in the controlled and known be encouraged.

We have focused on the two aspects of fostering creativity and inventions: the human side, i.e., the increase of potentially complex skills, and the technology side, where the usage of novel or unfamiliar technology increases. It should be noted that this setting is contextual in its nature, meaning that the increase of skill or technologies, and most of all, the complexity, novelty or unfamiliarity of them is judged in that specific context, for example within a specific course or a study program.

Figure 1 illustrates how the likelihood of creativity and invention changes as a function of novelty or unfamiliarity of technology used, and combination of skills required.

Fig. 1. Possibilities to learn, be creative and invent increase in relation to novelty and unfamiliarity of technology, or/and combination of required skills.

3 PLAYING SAFE?

In this article, we suggest that a possibility to be creative and invent already during studies will develop students' skills in several areas and equip them to working life challenges. Nevertheless, there is a doubt that the current engineering education does not allow students to learn the usage of their creativity and invention potential in a best possible way.

Nowadays, quality systems require well-defined learning outcomes, which definitely has its advantages. Eventually, however, university teachers decide what and how their students will learn in their courses. Increasing the number of possibilities, i.e., complexity of course exercises will complicate both students' and teachers' work during the course. This might draw teachers to play safe, and use the good old exercises that are familiar to them. However, some teachers certainly challenge their students and themselves, too.

It would be interesting to investigate the big picture of engineering education across the continent. How does current teaching support the development of the creativity and innovation potential of engineering students who will have the world in their hands after a decade or two?

3.1 Challenge to university teachers

We would like to challenge teachers to reflect their own courses. Are their students mostly equipped with the old solutions or are they supported to find also new ones - solutions that teachers cannot even think of? Surely, there are some courses that

support the development of working life skills, creativity and innovation, but how often will the teaching and learning still remain in a safe area that offers nothing new or risky? What are the barriers preventing or retarding the progress of having courses going to the direction of unfamiliar technologies and complex combinations of skills?

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